

SCHUMPETER'S VIEW ON ENTREPRENEUR AND CREDIT VERSUS CONTEMPORARY MEGA-BANKS PROBLEM

KAROL ŚLEDZIK

Considering Schumpeter's basic proposition about innovations as the strength of the capitalist dynamics, this paper focus on the main goal which is the answering the question: What was the Schumpeter's view on entrepreneur and credit versus modern mega-banks? The basic problems with the modern banks are mainly related with the level of concentration in the banking sector, the bonuses of the management (which are the derivative of bank's motivational systems) but most of all are related with phenomenon that the banking sector is pursuing goals, that are harmful to the long-term economic profitability. According to the Schumpeter banks should stimulate innovations implemented by etrepreneurs in the economy. Unfortunately the bankers nowadays seemed to have other priorities than those implied by their function in the economic system. According to Schumpeter credit contributes to the development, because development results from the activities of entrepreneurs. Other types of credit are not important from the point of view of "life process of the economic organism".

Schumpeter, bank, credit, money, mega-bank, big bank, innovation, entrepreneur

1. Introduction

Economics is the science which focuses on satisfying the needs, economic growth and welfare. This assumption is true for all schools in economics including Neoclassical, Keynesian and also the Schumpeterian economics. But the principles differs substantially among these various approaches. One of the significant differences of Schumpeterian economics (with respect to other approaches) is focusing on knowledge, innovation and entrepreneurship. The innovation is recognized as an main driver of economy competitiveness. It is true that knowledge and innovation was an area of interest to many economists. However it was Joseph Alois Schumpeter who considered the impact of technological innovation on an economy [1].

Today's knowledge-based economies are dependent by a dynamic technological progress. The generation of innovation no longer depends on individual personalities but involves the cooperation of many different subjects. One of the most important relations of those actors is relation entrepreneur-banker. It seems that Schumpeter's concepts are an ideal source of answers for today's relations of entrepreneur vs bank. Schumpeter was one of the first economists who put so considerable emphasis on money, credit, the role of the banker, innovation, entrepreneurship, knowledge, business cycles and economy development. One of the areas which Schumpeter was very interested in was the discus-

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sion on the transfer of capitalism into socialism. In 1928 Schumpeter wrote that "... capitalism is an economic system characterized by private property (private initiative), by production for a market and by the phenomenon of credit" [2]. Capitalism also means the search for prosperity initiated by the functioning of the market. It is a market-incorporated order built around private recognition of losses and private generation of profit. Capitalism, most distinctively of all, means bank creation of the means of payment. It is the unique contribution of bank finance, essential to the smooth functioning of entrepreneurship, that marks out the capitalist system as a mode of pecuniary self-expression quite unlike any other [3]. Considering banks functions in the economy we may say that: there is always a need to finance the innovative action on the market from the money bigger than companies savings. Unfortunately today's consolidated banks are dangerous from economic and public safety perspective. Furthermore today's banks became a "moral gambling" players under global economy conditions.

2. Problems with mega-banks

Today a huge portion of the world's financial transactions goes thru the small group of global institutions, whose mutual relationships in the international perspective are still growing. As a result of many years of consolidation and activity of banks in changing their size to such big that, in publications those banks was determined as "too big to fail (TBTF)", "too important to fail (TITF)", institutions important from the point of view of the system (SIFIs - Systemically important financial institutions), global financial institutions, multinational conglomerates, financial institutions with cross-border high-risk, or even large financial structures or eventually too large institutions to rescue them ("Too big to save – TBTS").

There is no specification what criteria should be used to identify the "big bank" or "mega-bank" in the economy. There is a proposal to make a statement of the total assets of the banking institution to the value of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the country in which the institution is registered. A problem arises, however, in the case of economies large enough that in vain to look for a bank that would have total assets in excess of GDP (e.g. United States) or countries so small, that most banks in the sector exceeds the sum of the carrying amount of the GDP (e.g. Switzerland).

Today functioning of mega-banks is related to several problems. For example total assets of 20 biggest banks in 2007 (before "subprime crisis") was about 22 trillion USD, which represented about 40% of the Gross World Product (about 54 trillion USD). This demonstrates the scale of the involvement of the largest banking institutions in the global economy. At the end of 2011, after four years of sub-prime crisis in the financial markets (where risk concerned entire economies), total assets of the 20 largest banks accounted for about 27 trillion of USD which represents about 34% of the Gross World Product (about 80 trillion of USD). It is worth noting that the 20 largest banks in the world with the end of 2011, manages the assets representing 26% of total assets in 1000 of the largest banks in the world (total assets of the 1000 largest banks in the world in 2011 was 101.6 trillion USD). The importance of the problem may indicate that two German banks in 2011

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have assets equal to 105 % of the GDP of the Germany. In the same year three French banks had assets at the level of 174 % of French GDP (see Table 1.).

Table 1 Selected indicators of the largest banks in 2011

	Bank	Country	Assets as % of GDP	Assets (mln USD)	Equity as % of liabilities	Equity (mln USD)
1	DEUTSCHE BANK	Germany	80,49	2 800 132	2,53	70 724
2	BNP PARIBAS	France	93,76	2 542 879	4,36	110 791
3	INDUSTRIAL & COMMERCIAL BANK OF CHINA	China	30,73	2 456 294	6,19	152 013
4	CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORPORATION	China	24,39	1 949 218	6,65	129 610
5	BANK OF CHINA LIMITED	China	23,49	1 877 520	6,39	119 966
6	AGRICULTURAL BANK OF CHINA LIMITED	China	23,19	1 853 318	5,56	103 126
7	BANCO SANTANDER	Spain	109,55	1 619 349	6,62	107 211
8	SOCIETE GENERALE	France	56,36	1 528 577	4,33	66 133
9	UBS	Switzerland	228,27	1 508 302	4,08	61 485
10	UNICREDIT	Italy	54,61	1 199 146	5,91	70 902
11	COMMERZBANK	Germany	24,61	856 255	3,75	32 092
12	INTESA SANPAOLO	Italy	37,66	827 088	7,47	61 794
13	ROYAL BANK OF CANADA	Canada	45,90	797 261	5,22	41 642
14	BANCO BILBAO VIZCAYA ARGENTARIA	Spain	52,32	773 348	6,70	51 831
15	NATIONAL AUSTRALIA BANK LIMITED	Australia	48,65	737 249	5,60	41 264
16	TORONTO DOMINION BANK	Canada	42,37	735 946	6,01	44 194
17	BANK OF COMMUNICATIONS	China	9,16	731 828	5,92	43 293
18	COMMONWEALTH BANK OF AUSTRALIA	Australia	47,33	717 256	5,58	40 042
19	NATIXIS	France	24,22	656 928	4,17	27 415
20	WESTPAC BANKING CORPORATION	Australia	43,26	655 550	6,54	42 848

Resource: Own calculation

Moral hazard is when institution is taking the risk and possible costs of failure are not compensated by this entity. When bank has almost as many assets as the GDP of the country in which is stationed we may define it as a hazard. When the big banks as a result of their conscious product strategy lead to a banking crisis and this causes intervention with the public money (taxpayers money) we are dealing with moral hazard. Before "sub-prime crisis" in 2008 there were considered several advantages of existing of the big banks as a result of consolidation processes. It was considered as modern direction of the changes in modern banking. The positive sides of this phenomenon were: economies of

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scale, standardization and internationalization of financial products, greater potential for innovation and positive change in the quality of human capital [9].

The disadvantages related to the functioning of mega-banks can include, for example:

- difficulty of supervising of mega-banks on an international (global) scale;
- mega-banks may be exposed to take risks in certain areas of activity;
- lack of transparency in reporting - problems in audit and ratings;
- In the context of TBTF institutions mega-banks cannot go through the procedures of bankruptcy;
- the problem of the international division of the cross-border insolvency costs;
- imperfect motivation systems based on bonuses for financial results which automatically exposures institution to risk;
- risk of instability of the state budget (financial support programs), and the bankruptcy of the country (including the example of Iceland);
- overgrowth of bank administrative apparatus combined with a small controllability and high complexity of the action;
- too extensive political connections.

The importance of the problem that occurred after the subprime crisis in the financial markets in 2008 can be proved by the following quote: "... owners of capital will stimulate the working class to buy more and more of expensive goods, houses and technology, pushing them to take more and more expensive credits, until their debt ... the unpaid debt will lead to bankruptcy of banks, which will have to be ... nationalized and you will come to a path that could lead to communism ... " [4]. Presented by Karl Marx sequence of events is in fact an abbreviation of description of the circulation of economic development. Marx identified the processes in capitalist economies, which sooner or later must lead to nationalization as a result of emerging problems and bankruptcies. A step further in its deliberations went Joseph A. Schumpeter. He was analyzing the impact of capitalism on the international economy taking into account that the end of the capitalist system is due to the transformation of the socialist system. However, according to Schumpeter's progressive transformation of capitalism into socialism is caused by its successes not by failures [5]. In Schumpeter's theory of economic development banks, mono- and oligopolistic companies has the essential place on the market. This gives grounds to believe that the mega-banks in the process of evolution may not only generate systemic risk at the micro level (country of origin), but also the risk of an international scale, which is so significant that it may lead to systemic changes in the economy. As Schumpeter writes in *Business Cycles*: "Capitalism is that form of private property economy in which innovations are carried out by means of borrowed money, which in general, though not by logical necessity, implies credit creation"[6].

3. Schumpeter's view on entrepreneur and credit

In the area of money and credit Schumpeter introduced two "heresies" (as he calls it) that differ from the mainstream of theoretical economics recognized in his times. First "heresy" consisted in the fact that the money in Schumpeter's view, was an independent

important function of the economy and was not just a passive reflection of the processes in the commodities market. Second "heresy" was that other means of payment also fulfill function of money. This is due to the fact that entrepreneur has to take a credit to be used for innovation. Schumpeter singled out two types of credit. The first is the traditional "normal" credit - that trade credit that results from the movement of goods, and is a certificate for goods or services already exist. The second is the traditional "abnormal" credit - which makes a claim for product for future goods and services. Thus gives rise to important Schumpeter's thesis which reads as follows: "Basically, anyone else as soon as the entrepreneur needs a loan". If it does not receive and will not become a debtor it will not become an entrepreneur [5].

According to Schumpeter credit contributes to the development, because development results from the activities of entrepreneurs. Other types of credit are not important from the point of view of "life process of the economic organism". Schumpeter believed that consumer credit is not a part of the economic process. Similarly operating credit (working capital credit) needed to keep the company in motion, is part of a circular flow. Second thesis concerns the sources of credit and reads as follows: "... the essence of the phenomenon of credit is thus to create new purchasing power serving only to extend credit for entrepreneur"[5]. Credit creation process can be, in accordance with the theoretical recognition of Schumpeter, regarded in its entirety as a "monetary complement of innovation". David Ricardo had said that the "veil of money" had no impact on the amount of capital. Differentiating cautiously between statics and dynamics, Schumpeter claimed conversely. At least in the imbalance term, he says, bank credit is "the specifically capitalist way of bringing about economic progress"[7].

The Banker is for Schumpeter a man who fulfills the important role of social and economy, because "he can carry out new combinations, authorizes people, as if on behalf of the society, to pursue them. He is an "ephor" of the economy". Opposite for the credit Schumpeter had very original opinion about savings. What is the most interesting is fact that Schumpeter many years before Keynes put forward the thesis that in a capitalist economy savings does not determine the size of investment, but investment determine size of savings [14].

The Schumpeterian banker is the money dealer- "the capitalist par excellence" [13] – furthermore Schumpeter extent two functions of the banker. First, he is a start-up entrants founder. Start-ups by definition have a low level of funding of their own. Besides for the company functioning in the market credit is much less important because corporation already has profits which cause different investment-competitive position in banking sector. Then new investments creates new profit and so on. Start-ups in contrast does not yet have profits or investments. What they do have is the "intangible" idea which should be collateral for the banker. According to Schumpeter it is clearly that lenders as well as entrepreneurs make capitalist development a practical possibility. Second function of the banker is that he is a screen, a filter and a judge all in one. Banks as a "for profit" companies have to take a view on the long-term projections of the projects. Not all investments can be financed by the banker because of the risk valuation effect. That is why the choice

of the banker, which depends on the risk-valuation tools, is the main function in the economy.

Nowadays for example in UK banking sector according to Miliband's analysis, "... the dominant banks are not lending enough to small and medium-sized enterprises because they form a cosy oligopoly (controlling 85% of small business lending) that does not want to take any risk; enterprise loans are inherently riskier than mortgage and personal loans. Given that small businesses create most jobs in the UK (as they do in all countries), lack of finance for them is limiting the creation of decent jobs. The solution, he argued, is to introduce more competition into the small business lending market by capping the share of individual banks ..." [8]. This tendency is actual for all developed economies and their banking sectors.

Bank should be an active creator not a passive broker in the economy. When bank is in the creating money process it also creates inflation. This bankers action can expand the nation's wealth: "The fact that bank money causes prices to rise is the cause of "forced savings". Even without the intention to save, a restriction of real incomes is brought about through the rise in prices. The consequence is that means of production are made free and the economic resources available for productive purposes increased" [7].

According to Schumpeter bankers credit means the "future". The entrepreneur - innovator upcoming the banker is making a pronouncement about the future history-to-come that he hopes to create: "The most typical embodiment of future values is a new undertaking" [5]. Credit may also mean the "past". In this perspective the banker must demonstrate a knowledge of the political and economic system, of the potential profits from specified sector, even of the particular borrower himself: "He must also know the customer, his business, and even his private habits". Schumpeter states that the demand and supply-side tools in the credit market are of questionable value. Moreover overestimates the ability of the interest rate as a tool to ensure balance on the financial market [6].

In Schumpeter's cyclical model of development, entrepreneurs receive from banks means of payment necessary for withdrawing the units of the labor services from the old productive units of the stationary state. It is necessary for entrepreneurs for the innovative or imitative processes. Schumpeter's conclusion is that any increase in the credit granted causes a further increase in the amount of financing which is needed for purchasing a specified amount of labor services and, therefore, a further increase in the demand for credit [7]. Schumpeter's vision of banks function in the economy is clear and specified. Unfortunately the strategy of mega-banks is far away of these assumptions.

4. Conclusions

Schumpeter's Theory of Economic Development has a special place in the history of economic thought. It is the original vision of economic development based on innovation and entrepreneurship, as a unique and creative driving force of this process resulted in numerous research works. Very important Schumpeter's merit was the emphasis on the relationship between bank credit obtained by the entrepreneur and economic develop-

ment. His pioneering findings were reflected in the turbulent capital market development in the modern world with all of the resulting positive and negative consequences.

The basic problems with the modern banks are mainly related with the level of concentration in the banking sector, the bonuses of the management (which a derivative of motivational systems) but most of all are related with phenomenon that the banking sector is pursuing goals that are harmful to the long-term economic profitability of the country engaging in the process enriching only a small minority and eroding at the same time human and financial resources from the rest of the economy. Oligopolistic mega-banks are entities which behavior on the market is in conflict with the Schumpeter's theories. What is even more important, mega-banks can create systemic mega-risk on global scale, which can be significant for the economy model.

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Karol Śledzik, PhD

University of Gdańsk
 Faculty of Management
 Department of Banking
 ul. Armii Krajowej 101
 81-824 Sopot, POLAND
 email: ksledzik@wzr.ug.edu.pl